

Biquaternion Construction of the Lorentz Transformation Operator in Relativistic Quantum Mechanics

E.P.J. de Haas

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Abstract The Lorentz transformation properties of the Dirac matrices remain a source of confusion in relativistic quantum mechanics. In standard presentations the covariance of the Dirac equation is guaranteed by assuming the existence of a transformation operator S satisfying $S\gamma^\nu S^{-1} = \Lambda_\mu^\nu \gamma^\mu$, and then solving for S . In this paper I take a constructive approach: starting from a biquaternion Pauli-level formalism that is morphologically equivalent to Minkowski space-time, I build the Weyl and Dirac matrix environments explicitly. By doubling the Pauli-level basis into a PT-duplex structure, the Weyl and Dirac β_μ matrices arise naturally as Clifford four-sets connected directly to space-time. From this basis, Lorentz transformation operators are constructed step by step, showing that the operator $S\Lambda S^{-1}$ follows from the algebra rather than being postulated.

This approach clarifies the apparent contradictions regarding whether Dirac matrices transform as four-vectors or remain inert, by demonstrating that in the Feynman slash objects $\not{P} = P_\mu \beta^\mu$ one may transform either the coordinates P_μ or the metric β^μ , but not both simultaneously. Spinor transformation rules and the mixing of Pauli spinors in the Dirac representation are derived constructively, revealing why the Pauli equation cannot be relativistic on its own.

The results provide a transparent biquaternion framework for the Lorentz covariance of relativistic wave equations, and may serve as a methodological clarification of the algebraic foundations of relativistic quantum mechanics.

Keywords: Relativistic Quantum Mechanics, Biquaternions, Dirac Equation, Lorentz Transformations

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1 Introduction

The Lorentz transformation properties of the Dirac matrices have been debated since their introduction. For some authors the gamma matrices are Lorentz-inert objects, even though they are written in a four-vector notation [1, p. 63], while for others they transform as ordinary four-vectors [2, p. 17]. The transformation of Dirac spinors is uncontroversial, but the situation is more ambiguous for the Dirac adjoint, which combines a spinor with the time-like gamma matrix γ^0 .

The difficulty arises because the gamma matrices occupy an intermediate position: they connect dynamical four-vectors such as momentum to the Minkowski metric, yet they are not themselves dynamical four-vectors. In standard treatments, Lorentz covariance of the Dirac equation is postulated, and one then solves for a transformation operator S satisfying $S\gamma^\nu S^{-1} = \Lambda_\mu{}^\nu \gamma^\mu$. In this approach S appears as an opaque object defined only through its required action [4–7], though critical alternatives exist [8].

In this paper I take a different route. Using a biquaternion framework that is morphologically equivalent to Minkowski space-time, I construct both the Weyl and Dirac representations explicitly from Pauli-level building blocks. In this setting the transformation operator S can be expressed directly as the composition of three elementary operations: a change of representation (Dirac→Weyl), a Lorentz boost in the Weyl representation, and the inverse change (Weyl→Dirac). This constructive derivation replaces the usual postulate-and-solve method with a transparent algebraic procedure.

The paper is organized in two parts. Part I develops the Pauli-level biquaternion formalism and applies it to mechanics and electrodynamics. While this first step resonates with earlier biquaternion approaches proposed over the last century [9, 10], it is not a mere repetition. The Pauli-level construction here is deliberately shaped to anticipate the Dirac–Weyl framework: it embeds spin within a space-time metric that can be internally Doppler-twisted, thereby laying the groundwork for the treatment of Lorentz covariance at the Dirac level. The application to the Maxwell and Lorentz equations serves not only to demonstrate mathematical and conceptual consistency, but also to prepare the structural bridge that Part II will extend to relativistic quantum mechanics.

Part II constructs the Weyl–Dirac environment as a PT-doubling of the Pauli framework. This yields the gamma matrices, the Lorentz transformation operators, and the spinor transformation laws, clarifying the status of the gamma matrices and their relation to Minkowski space-time.

2 The Pauli spin level

2.1 A complex quaternion basis for the metric

Quaternions can be represented by the basis $(\hat{\mathbf{1}}, \hat{\mathbf{i}}, \hat{\mathbf{j}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})$. This basis has the properties $\hat{\mathbf{i}}\hat{\mathbf{i}} = \hat{\mathbf{j}}\hat{\mathbf{j}} = \hat{\mathbf{k}}\hat{\mathbf{k}} = -\hat{\mathbf{1}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{i}}\hat{\mathbf{i}} = \hat{\mathbf{i}}$; $\hat{\mathbf{i}}\hat{\mathbf{i}} = \hat{\mathbf{i}}$, $\hat{\mathbf{i}}\hat{\mathbf{j}} = \hat{\mathbf{j}}\hat{\mathbf{i}} = \hat{\mathbf{j}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{i}}\hat{\mathbf{k}} = \hat{\mathbf{k}}\hat{\mathbf{i}} = \hat{\mathbf{k}}$; $\hat{\mathbf{i}}\hat{\mathbf{j}} = -\hat{\mathbf{j}}\hat{\mathbf{i}} = \hat{\mathbf{k}}$; $\hat{\mathbf{j}}\hat{\mathbf{k}} = -\hat{\mathbf{k}}\hat{\mathbf{j}} = \hat{\mathbf{i}}$; $\hat{\mathbf{k}}\hat{\mathbf{i}} = -\hat{\mathbf{i}}\hat{\mathbf{k}} = \hat{\mathbf{j}}$. A quaternion number in its summation representation is given by $A = a_0\hat{\mathbf{1}} + a_1\hat{\mathbf{i}} + a_2\hat{\mathbf{j}} + a_3\hat{\mathbf{k}}$, in which the a_μ are real numbers. Bi-quaternions or complex quaternions are given by $C = A + \mathbf{i}B = c_0\hat{\mathbf{1}} + c_1\hat{\mathbf{i}} + c_2\hat{\mathbf{j}} + c_3\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ in which the $c_\mu = a_\mu + \mathbf{i}b_\mu$ are complex numbers and the a_μ and b_μ are real numbers.

This standard biquaternion basis $(\hat{\mathbf{1}}, \hat{\mathbf{i}}, \hat{\mathbf{j}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})$ can be used to provide a basis for relativistic 4-D space-time. One way to do this is by making the time coordinate $c_0 = b_0\mathbf{i}$ complex only and the space coordinates $(c_1, c_2, c_3) = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ real only, see [11]. Synge called these objects Minkowski quaternions or ‘minquats’, Silberstein called them ‘physical quaternions’ [11]. This however produces confusion regarding the time-like complex number as the physics gets more complicated. As Synge put it, *the intrusion of the imaginary element is not trivial* [11]. The main reason is that minquats do not form a closed algebra under addition and multiplication as a subspace inside the wider biquaternion space, due to the multiplication operation. The reason they are used nevertheless is given by Synge: *For the application of quaternions to Lorentz transformations it is essential to introduce Minkowskian quaternions* [11].

The use of minquats produces language conflicts with almost all of modern physics, that is Quantum Mechanics and Special and General Relativity, where the space-time coordinates always are a set of four real numbers. So for several reasons, I choose to insert the time-like complex number of $c_0 = b_0\mathbf{i}$ in the basis instead of in the coordinate. So by using $c_0\hat{\mathbf{1}} = b_0\mathbf{i}\hat{\mathbf{1}} = b_0\hat{\mathbf{T}}$ the space-time basis is then given by $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \hat{\mathbf{i}}, \hat{\mathbf{j}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})$. In this way, the coordinates are always a set of real numbers $\in \mathbb{R}$. The space-time basis $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \hat{\mathbf{i}}, \hat{\mathbf{j}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}})$, (a disguised minquat basis) is not closed under multiplications, as already mentioned by Synge.

Remark. In earlier approaches (e.g. Synge’s minquats), the imaginary unit is placed in the time coordinate, $c_0 = \mathbf{i}b_0$. However, after quaternion multiplication this imaginary factor propagates into the spatial components, so one must continually keep track of where the \mathbf{i} has moved in the algebra. By inserting the imaginary unit once and for all into the basis element $\hat{\mathbf{T}} = \mathbf{i}\hat{\mathbf{1}}$, the coordinates themselves remain real and the metric automatically records the complex character of the time component. This avoids the need for such bookkeeping. A second reason is more intuitive and rooted in physics and in the comparison with general relativity: in GR the coordinates of a four-vector are always real numbers, and consequently the tensors and matrices built from them are real as well. By keeping all coordinates

real in the present biquaternion framework, the algebra mirrors this feature of GR, which will later allow a direct comparison between the GR formalism and the present biquaternion language.

A set of four numbers $\in \mathbb{R}$ is given by

$$A^\mu = \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix},$$

or by $A_\mu = [a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3]$. In this way, the raising or lowering of the index doesn't change any sign. A^μ simply is the transpose of A_μ and vice versa.¹ The biquaternion basis can be given as a set $\mathbf{K}_\mu = (\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \hat{\mathbf{I}}, \hat{\mathbf{J}}, \hat{\mathbf{K}})$. Then a biquaternion space-time vector can be written as the product

$$A = A_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = [a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3] \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{T}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{I}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{J}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{K}} \end{bmatrix} = a_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}} + a_1 \hat{\mathbf{I}} + a_2 \hat{\mathbf{J}} + a_3 \hat{\mathbf{K}} \quad (1)$$

I apply this to the space-time four vector of relativistic bi-quaternion 4-space R with the four numbers $R_\mu = (r_0, r_1, r_2, r_3) = (ct, r_1, r_2, r_3)$, so with $r_0, r_1, r_2, r_3 \in \mathbb{R}$. Then I have the space-time four-vector as the product of the coordinate set and the basis $R = R_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = r_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}} + r_1 \hat{\mathbf{I}} + r_2 \hat{\mathbf{J}} + r_3 \hat{\mathbf{K}} = ct \hat{\mathbf{T}} + \mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{K}$. I use the three-vector analogue of $R_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu$ when I write $\mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{K}$. In this notation I have $R^T = -r_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}} + r_1 \hat{\mathbf{I}} + r_2 \hat{\mathbf{J}} + r_3 \hat{\mathbf{K}} = -r_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}} + \mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{K}$ for the time reversal operator and $R^P = r_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}} - r_1 \hat{\mathbf{I}} - r_2 \hat{\mathbf{J}} - r_3 \hat{\mathbf{K}} = r_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}} - \mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{K}$ for the space point mirror or parity operator.²

Having established the complex quaternion basis $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \hat{\mathbf{I}}, \hat{\mathbf{J}}, \hat{\mathbf{K}})$, it is useful to connect this abstract algebraic framework to an explicit matrix representation. Such a representation allows the biquaternion formalism to be handled with standard linear algebra tools and facilitates comparison with the Pauli spin matrices. In the

¹ In standard Minkowski space-time with metric signature $(-, +, +, +)$, raising or lowering indices introduces a sign change in the temporal component, e.g. $A_0 = -A^0$. In the present biquaternion framework, however, raising and lowering indices is defined purely algebraically as matrix transposition, so A^μ is simply the transpose of A_μ . The Minkowski metric structure enters later through the multiplication properties of the basis elements, not through index manipulation.

² Note that, by direct calculation, the parity operator satisfies $R^P = -R^T$. In this notation, the transpose of a matrix is denoted by the suffix 't', so $R_\mu^t = R^\mu$. The Hermitian (complex) transpose of spinors is indicated by the dagger symbol, as in ψ^\dagger , and the complex conjugate by ψ^* . Within this framework, the discrete symmetry operators T and P implement sign changes of temporal and spatial components, in a way that is formally analogous to the index manipulations induced by the metric in general relativity.

next subsection I therefore represent the basis elements as 2×2 complex matrices and show how a four-vector acquires a compact matrix form in this setting.

2.2 Matrix representation of the quaternion basis

Quaternions can be represented by 2×2 matrices. Several representations are possible, but most of those choices result in conflict with the standard approach in physics. Given the unit quaternion as $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$, my choice for the space-time four set is

$$\hat{\mathbf{T}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{i} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{i} \end{bmatrix}, \hat{\mathbf{I}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{i} & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathbf{i} \end{bmatrix}, \hat{\mathbf{J}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \hat{\mathbf{K}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{i} & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

I can compare these to the Pauli spin matrices $\sigma_P = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)$.

$$\sigma_x = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \sigma_y = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{i} & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \sigma_z = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

If I exchange the σ_x and the σ_z ³, I get $\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{i}\sigma$ and $\mathbf{K}_\mu = \mathbf{i}(\hat{\mathbf{I}}, \sigma)$. So in my use of the Pauli matrices, I use $\sigma \equiv (\sigma_I, \sigma_J, \sigma_K) = (\sigma_z, \sigma_y, \sigma_x)$. So also $\hat{\mathbf{I}} = \hat{\mathbf{T}}\sigma_I$, $\hat{\mathbf{J}} = \hat{\mathbf{T}}\sigma_J$, $\hat{\mathbf{K}} = \hat{\mathbf{T}}\sigma_K$ and $\sigma_I = -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{I}}$, $\sigma_J = -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{J}}$, $\sigma_K = -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}}$.

With this choice of matrices, a four-vector R can be written as

$$R = r_0 \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{i} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{i} \end{bmatrix} + r_1 \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{i} & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathbf{i} \end{bmatrix} + r_2 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + r_3 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{i} & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

This can be compacted into a matrix representation of R :

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} r_0\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{i}r_1 & r_2 + \mathbf{i}r_3 \\ -r_2 + \mathbf{i}r_3 & r_0\mathbf{i} - \mathbf{i}r_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_{00} & R_{01} \\ R_{10} & R_{11} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

with the numbers $R_{00}, R_{01}, R_{10}, R_{11} \in \mathbb{C}$. Thus a Minkowski four-vector can be represented as a 2×2 complex matrix, with its algebra inherited from the quaternion basis.

2.3 Multiplication of vectors as matrix multiplication adds pauliquats to minquats

In general, the multiplication of two four-vectors A and B follows matrix multiplication, with $A_{ij}, B_{ij}, C_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}$.

$$AB = \begin{bmatrix} A_{00} & A_{01} \\ A_{10} & A_{11} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} B_{00} & B_{01} \\ B_{10} & B_{11} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{00} & C_{01} \\ C_{10} & C_{11} \end{bmatrix} = C. \quad (6)$$

³ This unconventional ordering simplifies the identification with the quaternion basis introduced above.

So we have

$$C = AB = \begin{bmatrix} A_{00}B_{00} + A_{01}B_{10} & A_{00}B_{01} + A_{01}B_{11} \\ A_{10}B_{00} + A_{11}B_{10} & A_{10}B_{01} + A_{11}B_{11} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{00} & C_{01} \\ C_{10} & C_{11} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

Of course, vectors A , B and C can be expressed with their a_μ, b_μ, c_μ coordinates $\in \mathbb{R}$ and if we use them, after some elementary but elaborate calculations and rearrangements we arrive at the following result of the multiplication expressed in the a_μ, b_μ and c_μ as ⁴:

$$\begin{aligned} c_0 &= -a_0b_0 - a_1b_1 - a_2b_2 - a_3b_3 \\ c_{1K} &= a_2b_3 - a_3b_2 \\ c_{2K} &= a_3b_1 - a_1b_3 \\ c_{3K} &= a_1b_2 - a_2b_1 \\ c_{1\sigma} &= -a_0b_1 - a_1b_0 \\ c_{2\sigma} &= -a_0b_2 - a_2b_0 \\ c_{3\sigma} &= -a_0b_3 - a_3b_0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In short, if we use the three-dimensional Euclidean dot and cross products of Euclidean three-vectors in classical physics, this gives for the coordinates

$$\begin{aligned} c_0 &= -a_0b_0 - \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} \\ \mathbf{c}_K &= \mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{c}_\sigma = -a_0\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{a}b_0 \quad (10)$$

And in the quaternion notation we get

$$C = AB = (-a_0b_0 - \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b})\hat{\mathbf{1}} + (\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b}) \cdot \mathbf{K} + (-a_0\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{a}b_0) \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (11)$$

This matrix multiplication, in which I used $\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{T}} = -\hat{\mathbf{1}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{T}}\mathbf{K} = -\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, implies that the space-time basis $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \mathbf{K})$ is being duplicated by a spin-norm basis $(\hat{\mathbf{1}}, \boldsymbol{\sigma})$ by the multiplication operation.

The relativistically relevant multiplications of two four-vectors are all in the form $C = A^T B$. The difference between AB and $A^T B$ is in the sign of a_0 . This results in

$$C = A^T B = (a_0b_0 - \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b})\hat{\mathbf{1}} + (\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b}) \cdot \mathbf{K} + (a_0\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{a}b_0) \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (12)$$

Hence the relativistically relevant bilinear is $A^T B$, not AB , and the invariant quadratic is $A^T A$:

$$C = A^T A = (a_0^2 - \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{a})\hat{\mathbf{1}} = c^2 a_\tau^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}},$$

⁴ Here the subscripts K and σ denote the parts in the \mathbf{K} and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ directions, respectively.

The main quadratic form of the metric is $dR^T dR = (c^2 dt^2 - d\mathbf{r}^2)\hat{\mathbf{1}} = c^2 d\tau^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}} = ds^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}}$ with $ds = cd\tau$. The quadratic giving the distance of a point R to the origin of its reference system is given by $R^T R = (c^2 t^2 - \mathbf{r}^2)\hat{\mathbf{1}} = c^2 \tau^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}} = s^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}}$ with $s = c\tau$.

The multiplication of two four vectors can also be arranged as the multiplication of two tensors, a coordinate tensor times a metric tensor using that

$$(A_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu)^T B_\nu \mathbf{K}^\nu = A_\mu B^\nu (\mathbf{K}_\mu)^T \mathbf{K}^\nu = C_\mu{}^\nu \mathbf{K}_\mu{}^\nu \quad (13)$$

with a real coordinate tensor $C_\mu{}^\nu$ ⁵. Using multiplication rules as $\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{T}} = -\hat{\mathbf{1}}$, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{I}} = -\sigma_I$, $\hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{T}} = \sigma_I$ and others, the metric tensor can be expanded as

$$\mathbf{K}_\mu{}^\nu = (\mathbf{K}_\mu)^T \mathbf{K}^\nu = \begin{bmatrix} -\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \hat{\mathbf{I}}, \hat{\mathbf{J}}, \hat{\mathbf{K}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{T}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{I}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{J}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{K}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{T}} & \hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{I}} & \hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{I}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{I}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{J}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{J}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} & \hat{\mathbf{J}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} & \hat{\mathbf{K}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{1}} & -\sigma_I & -\sigma_J & -\sigma_K \\ \sigma_I & -\hat{\mathbf{1}} & -\hat{\mathbf{K}} & \hat{\mathbf{J}} \\ \sigma_J & \hat{\mathbf{K}} & -\hat{\mathbf{1}} & -\hat{\mathbf{I}} \\ \sigma_K & -\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}} & -\hat{\mathbf{1}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

This multiplication product has a norm $\hat{\mathbf{1}}$ part, a space \mathbf{K} part and a spin σ part. So the multiplication of two four vectors $A^T B = C$ has this multiplication matrix. The multiplication combines the properties of symmetric and anti-symmetric in one product: the scalar part ($\propto \hat{\mathbf{1}}$) is symmetric in A, B , the \mathbf{K} part ($\propto \mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b}$) is antisymmetric, and the σ part mixes them through the temporal–spatial coupling.

The inevitable appearance of the spin-norm basis in the multiplication of two Synge minquats or Silberstein physical quaternions explains why the minquats do not form a closed algebra under multiplication [11]. In the present approach, the space-time basis $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \mathbf{K})$ likewise does not form a closed algebra by itself: it requires a spin-norm complex dual $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \mathbf{K}) = \mathbf{i}(\hat{\mathbf{I}}, \sigma)$ in order to span the full biquaternion space. This extension is obtained under the deliberate convention—a free choice of framework in the Kantian sense—to restrict all coordinates R_μ, P_μ in $R_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu$ and $P_\mu \sigma^\mu$ to real values. That convention uniquely produces the dual basis.

Interpretive remark. One may view the resulting structure as endowing the physical domain with a dual space-time/spin-norm basis as its natural geometry. Speculatively, this duality might mirror aspects of real physics: electric charges and currents

⁵ Here the coefficients $C_\mu{}^\nu$ are built purely from the real-number components A_μ and B^ν , while the geometric content of the multiplication resides in the metric basis $(\mathbf{K}_\mu)^T \mathbf{K}^\nu$. This separation mirrors the situation in special and general relativity, where tensors are expressed as coordinate arrays of real numbers contracted with basis elements determined by the metric. In this way, the biquaternion formalism reproduces the same division between numerical components and geometric structure that underlies SR and GR.

reside in the space-time sector $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \mathbf{K})$, whereas hypothetical magnetic monopoles and monopole currents, if they exist, would be associated with the spin-norm sector $(\hat{\mathbf{I}}, \boldsymbol{\sigma})$.

In this terminology, Synge's minquats correspond to $R_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu$ biquaternions, while $P_\mu \boldsymbol{\sigma}^\mu$ may be called pauliquats. Together, minquats and pauliquats span the full biquaternion space. The multiplication of two minquats necessarily produces both a minquat and a pauliquat component. In this picture, electric currents are naturally represented by minquats, magnetic currents (if at all possible) by pauliquats. Intrinsic spin appears as a pauliquat, with its Lorentz dual—intrinsic polarization—as a minquat. This asymmetric pairing of minquats and pauliquats stands in contrast to the electromagnetic supersymmetry sought by some magnetic-monopole approaches.

2.4 The Lorentz transformation

A standard Lorentz transformation between two reference frames connected by a relative velocity v in the x - or $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ -direction, with the usual $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$, $\beta = v/c$ and $r_0 = ct$, can be expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} r'_0 \\ r'_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma & -\beta\gamma \\ -\beta\gamma & \gamma \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} r_0 \\ r_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma r_0 - \beta\gamma r_1 \\ \gamma r_1 - \beta\gamma r_0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (16)$$

We want to connect this to our matrix representation of R as in Eq.(5) which gives

$$R'_{00} = \mathbf{i}r'_0 + \mathbf{i}r'_1 = \mathbf{i}\gamma r_0 - \mathbf{i}\beta\gamma r_1 + \mathbf{i}\gamma r_1 - \mathbf{i}\beta\gamma r_0 \quad (17)$$

$$R'_{11} = \mathbf{i}r'_0 - \mathbf{i}r'_1 = \mathbf{i}\gamma r_0 - \mathbf{i}\beta\gamma r_1 - \mathbf{i}\gamma r_1 + \mathbf{i}\beta\gamma r_0. \quad (18)$$

Now we want to introduce rapidity or hyperbolic Special Relativity in order to integrate Lorentz transformations into our matrix metric. In [12] I gave a brief history of rapidity in its relation to the Thomas precession and the geodesic precession. For this paper we only need elementary rapidity definitions. If we use the rapidity ψ as

$$e^{\pm\psi} = \gamma \pm \beta\gamma, \quad \cosh \psi = \gamma, \quad \sinh \psi = \beta\gamma, \quad e^{\pm\psi} = \cosh \psi \pm \sinh \psi, \quad (19)$$

the previous transformations can be rewritten as

$$R'_{00} = \mathbf{i}r'_0 + \mathbf{i}r'_1 = (\gamma - \beta\gamma)(\mathbf{i}r_0 + \mathbf{i}r_1) = R_{00}e^{-\psi} \quad (20)$$

$$R'_{11} = \mathbf{i}r'_0 - \mathbf{i}r'_1 = (\gamma + \beta\gamma)(\mathbf{i}r_0 - \mathbf{i}r_1) = R_{11}e^{\psi}. \quad (21)$$

As a result we have

$$R^L = \begin{bmatrix} R'_{00} & R'_{01} \\ R'_{10} & R'_{11} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_{00}e^{-\psi} & R_{01} \\ R_{10} & R_{11}e^{\psi} \end{bmatrix} = U^{-1}RU^{-1}. \quad (22)$$

The appearance of U^{-1} on both sides reflects that boosts scale the basis elements $\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \hat{\mathbf{I}}$ oppositely; the off-diagonal entries remain unchanged (since r_2, r_3 are invariant under an $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ -aligned boost and the factors cancel). In the expression $R^L = U^{-1}RU^{-1}$ we used the matrix U as

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\frac{\psi}{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-\frac{\psi}{2}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

But this means that we can write the result of a Lorentz transformation on R with a Lorentz velocity in the $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ -direction between the two reference systems as

$$R^L = r_0 \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{i}e^{-\psi} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{i}e^{\psi} \end{bmatrix} + r_1 \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{i}e^{-\psi} & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathbf{i}e^{\psi} \end{bmatrix} + r_2 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + r_3 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{i} & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (24)$$

This can be written as

$$R^L = r_0 U^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{T}} U^{-1} + r_1 U^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{I}} U^{-1} + r_2 \hat{\mathbf{J}} + r_3 \hat{\mathbf{K}} = r_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}}^L + r_1 \hat{\mathbf{I}}^L + r_2 \hat{\mathbf{J}} + r_3 \hat{\mathbf{K}}. \quad (25)$$

But because we started with Eq.(16), we now have two equivalent options to express the result of a Lorentz transformation

$$R^L = r'_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}} + r'_1 \hat{\mathbf{I}} + r_2 \hat{\mathbf{J}} + r_3 \hat{\mathbf{K}} = r_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}}^L + r_1 \hat{\mathbf{I}}^L + r_2 \hat{\mathbf{J}} + r_3 \hat{\mathbf{K}}, \quad (26)$$

either as a coordinate transformation or as a basis transformation.

This result only works for Lorentz transformation between v_x -, v_1 - or $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ -aligned reference systems. Reference systems which do not have their relative Lorentz velocity aligned in the $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ -direction will have to be space rotated into such an alignment before the Lorentz transformation in the form $R^L = U^{-1}RU^{-1}$ is applied. In principle, such a rotation in order to achieve the $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ alignment of the primary reference frame to a secondary reference frame is always possible as an operation prior to a Lorentz transformation. This unique alignment between two frames of reference S and S' , needed to match the physics with the algebra, is analyzed by Synge in [11, p. 41-48] and focuses on the concept of a communal photon. The requirement of reference system alignment is also the reason for the appearance of the Thomas precession and the Thomas-Wigner rotation if the axes are not aligned; the notion that two Lorentz transformations in different directions in space can always be substituted by the subsequent application of one space rotation and one single Lorentz transformation, see [12]. The communal photon of Synge is the one

for which the relativistic Doppler shift between S and S' results in $\nu' = \nu e^{\pm\psi}$. The minquat algebra requires inertial observers to align their principal axis along such a communal photon, in my notation the $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ axis.

The Lorentz transformation of the coordinates $(R^\mu)^L$ can be written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} r'_0 \\ r'_1 \\ r'_2 \\ r'_3 \end{bmatrix} = \Lambda_\nu^\mu R^\nu = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma & -\gamma\beta & 0 & 0 \\ -\gamma\beta & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} r_0 \\ r_1 \\ r_2 \\ r_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma r_0 - \beta\gamma r_1 \\ \gamma r_1 - \beta\gamma r_0 \\ r_2 \\ r_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

So the Lorentz transformation of $R = R_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = \mathbf{K}_\mu R^\mu$ can be presented as

$$\begin{aligned} R^L &= \mathbf{K}_\mu (R^\mu)^L = \mathbf{K}_\mu \Lambda_\nu^\mu R^\nu = (\mathbf{K}_\mu \Lambda_\nu^\mu) R^\nu = (\mathbf{K}_\nu)^L R^\nu \\ &= U^{-1} \mathbf{K}_\nu U^{-1} R^\nu = U^{-1} \mathbf{K}_\nu R^\nu U^{-1} = U^{-1} R U^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Lemma 1 (derived). For boosts along $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$, the explicit calculation of the transformed matrix elements in (22)–(27) shows that the biquaternion basis $\mathbf{K}_\mu = (\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \hat{\mathbf{I}}, \hat{\mathbf{J}}, \hat{\mathbf{K}})$ satisfies

$$\boxed{\mathbf{K}_\mu \Lambda_\nu^\mu = U^{-1} \mathbf{K}_\nu U^{-1}}.$$

This identity is therefore not an assumption but the algebraic consequence of the biquaternion representation of R and the standard Lorentz transformation of its coordinates. In particular, it provides the constructive link between the coordinate transformation law and the transformation of the basis, so that later the transformation properties of the Dirac equation can be proved from this construction rather than postulated. We can now formulate the lemma more tightly and emphasize its bidirectional use, once its derivation has been established:

Lemma 1 (Basis–component compatibility for $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ -aligned boosts) *Let Λ_ν^μ be the Lorentz boost in the $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ -direction, and $U = \text{diag}(e^{\psi/2}, e^{-\psi/2})$ as in (23). Then the biquaternion basis $\mathbf{K}_\mu = (\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \hat{\mathbf{I}}, \hat{\mathbf{J}}, \hat{\mathbf{K}})$ satisfies*

$$\boxed{\mathbf{K}_\mu \Lambda_\nu^\mu = U^{-1} \mathbf{K}_\nu U^{-1}}, \quad (28)$$

and therefore $R^L = \mathbf{K}_\mu (R^\mu)^L = (U^{-1} \mathbf{K}_\nu U^{-1}) R^\nu = U^{-1} R U^{-1}$.

This lemma will serve as the cornerstone for the later derivation of the Lorentz transformation properties of the Dirac equation: because the gamma matrices are built from these basis elements, their transformation laws follow directly from Lemma 1, and thus are proved from construction rather than assumed.

The identity (Lemma 1) has no analogue for coordinates alone: numerical components cannot satisfy a conjugation relation, whereas the matrix-valued basis does. The matrix representation of the basis is key to this identity, because the

relativistic Doppler factor $e^{\pm\psi}$ appears differently attached to the matrix elements. As is the $\hat{\mathbf{1}}$ alignment of the two involved reference frames during the Lorentz transformation. Given that $\mathbf{K}_\mu = \mathbf{i}\sigma_\mu$, the identity $\mathbf{K}_\mu \Lambda_\nu^\mu = U^{-1} \mathbf{K}_\nu U^{-1}$ can also be seen as an instruction for the Lorentz transformation of the Pauli spin matrices as a norm-spin four set $\sigma_\mu = (\hat{\mathbf{1}}, \boldsymbol{\sigma})$.

The Lorentz transformation of A^T is also interesting, due to the importance of the product $C = A^T B$ and therefore the Lorentz transformation C^L . Given the inverse Lorentz transformation as

$$A^{L^{-1}} \equiv UAU \quad (29)$$

and using $U^T = U$ since U is real diagonal, one can prove

$$\left(A^T\right)^{L^{-1}} = U \left(A^T\right) U = \left(U^{-1} A U^{-1}\right)^T = \left(A^L\right)^T \quad (30)$$

and

$$\left(A^T\right)^L = U^{-1} \left(A^T\right) U^{-1} = \left(UAU\right)^T = \left(A^{L^{-1}}\right)^T. \quad (31)$$

The result $\left(A^L\right)^T = U A^T U$ will be used in several important derivations in this paper, when the Lorentz transformation of a product and the possible invariance or Lorentz covariance has to be investigated, as in the next example.

Start with two inertial reference systems S_1 and S_2 connected by a constant relative velocity v , a Lorentz gamma factor $\gamma(v)$ and a rapidity factor $\psi(v)$ defining the Lorentz transformation matrix U . Given A and B in S_1 and their product in S_1 as $C = A^T B$. Then in S_2 one has A^L and B^L and their product $C^L = \left(A^L\right)^T B^L$. We then have

$$\begin{aligned} C^L &= \left(A^L\right)^T B^L = \left(A^T\right)^{L^{-1}} B^L = U \left(A^T\right) U U^{-1} B U^{-1} \\ &= U A^T B U^{-1} = U C U^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

As a result, it is easy to prove that the quadratic $A^T A = c^2 a_\tau^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}}$ is Lorentz invariant. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \left(A^L\right)^T A^L &= \left(A^T\right)^{L^{-1}} A^L = U A^T U U^{-1} A U^{-1} = U \left(A^T A\right) U^{-1} \\ &= U \left(c^2 a_\tau^2\right) \hat{\mathbf{1}} U^{-1} = U U^{-1} \left(c^2 a_\tau^2\right) \hat{\mathbf{1}} = c^2 a_\tau^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}} = A^T A. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

So both quadratics $R^T R$ and $dR^T dR$ are Lorentz invariant scalars, as has been shown for every quadratic of four-vectors. But they aren't what we consider to be *perfect quadratics*, who we define through the requirement $AA = |A|^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}}$.

2.5 Adding the dynamic vectors

If I want to apply the previous to relativistic electrodynamics and to quantum physics, I need to further develop the mathematical language, the notation system and the biquaternion elements. I don't claim originality regarding the biquaternion foundations of my notation system. As indicated before, there is a whole subculture around quaternions and biquaternions in physics, see [9], [10], and I have been studying many of those papers. The justification for my paper is to be found in what it adds to this rather large subculture, as part of the more general *plethora of different vector formalisms currently in use* [13].

But let's return to my project of formulating a pragmatic biquaternion mathematical-physical language through which relativity and quantum can be synthesized. The most relevant dynamic four-vectors must be given a biquaternion representation. The basic definitions I use for that purpose are quite common in the formulations of relativistic dynamics, see for example [14]. I start with a particle with a given three vector velocity as \mathbf{v} , a rest mass as m_0 and an inertial mass $m_i = \gamma m_0$, with the usual $\gamma = (\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2})^{-1}$. Latin suffixes are labels only and never imply summation; Greek suffixes always imply summation over the numbers 0, 1, 2 and 3.. So m_i stands for inertial mass and U_p for potential energy and P_μ stands for a momentum four-vector coordinate row with components $(p_0 = \frac{1}{c}U_i, p_1, p_2, p_3)$, with U_i being the inertial energy (total relativistic energy). The momentum three-vector is written as \mathbf{p} and has components (p_1, p_2, p_3) .

I define the coordinate velocity four-vector as

$$V = V_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = \frac{d}{dt} R_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = c \hat{\mathbf{T}} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{K} = v_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{K}. \quad (34)$$

The proper velocity four-vector on the other hand will be defined using the proper time $\tau = t_0$, with $t = \gamma t_0 = \gamma \tau$ as

$$U = U_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = \frac{d}{d\tau} R_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = \frac{d}{\frac{1}{\gamma} dt} R_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = \gamma V_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = u_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{K}. \quad (35)$$

So we have $v_0 = c$ and $u_0 = \gamma c$.

The momentum four-vector will be, at least when we have the symmetry condition $\mathbf{p} = m_i \mathbf{v}$,

$$P = P_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = m_i V_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = m_i V = m_0 U_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu = m_0 U. \quad (36)$$

The quadratic of the momentum four-vector $P^T P$ is important in relativity and is at the basis of the Klein-Gordon equation, so we give it here in our formalism:

$$P^T P = (U_i^2/c^2 - \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}) \hat{\mathbf{1}} = U_0^2/c^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}} = E^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}}, \quad (37)$$

with the shorthand notation $E := U_0/c$. This scalar invariant will reappear in the Weyl and Dirac constructions as the quadratic relation that their linearized equations reproduce.

The four-vector partial derivative $\partial = \partial_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu$ will be defined using the coordinate four set

$$\partial_\mu = \left[-\frac{1}{c} \partial_t, \nabla_1, \nabla_2, \nabla_3 \right] = [\partial_0, \partial_1, \partial_2, \partial_3]. \quad (38)$$

Remark. In standard Minkowski notation the minus sign in $\partial_0 = -\frac{1}{c} \partial_t$ reflects the $(- + ++)$ metric signature. In the present framework, however, this minus sign stems from having shifted the imaginary unit from the coordinate $\mathbf{i}ct$ into the basis element $\hat{\mathbf{T}} = \mathbf{i}\hat{\mathbf{1}}$. The minus sign thus arises here as a direct consequence of the basis construction because $\frac{1}{\mathbf{i}ct} \hat{\mathbf{1}} = -\mathbf{i} \frac{1}{ct} \hat{\mathbf{1}} = -\frac{1}{ct} \hat{\mathbf{T}}$. This ensures that $-\partial^T \partial = (-\frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t^2 + \nabla^2) \hat{\mathbf{1}}$, which reproduces the standard Minkowski form of the d'Alembert operator.

The electrodynamic potential four-vector $A = A_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu$ will be defined by the coordinate four set

$$A_\mu = \left[\frac{1}{c} \phi, A_1, A_2, A_3 \right] = [A_0, A_1, A_2, A_3] \quad (39)$$

The electric four current density vector $J = J_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu$ will be defined by the coordinate four set

$$J_\mu = [c\rho_e, J_1, J_2, J_3] = [J_0, J_1, J_2, J_3], \quad (40)$$

with ρ_e as the electric charge density. The electric four current with a charge q will be also be written as J_μ and the context will indicate which one is used.

Although we defined these four-vectors using the coordinate column notation, we will often use the matrix or summation notation, as for example with $P = P_\mu \mathbf{K}^\mu$, written as

$$\begin{aligned} P &= p_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}} + p_1 \hat{\mathbf{1}} + p_2 \hat{\mathbf{J}} + p_3 \hat{\mathbf{K}} = p_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{K} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{i}p_0 + \mathbf{i}p_1 & p_2 + \mathbf{i}p_3 \\ -p_2 + \mathbf{i}p_3 & \mathbf{i}p_0 - \mathbf{i}p_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} P_{00} & P_{01} \\ P_{10} & P_{11} \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

The flexibility to use either of these notations is a strength of the mathematical–physical language as developed in this paper. There are cases where one needs to go all the way to the internal scalar matrix notation to solve issues as for example the product rule in calculating a derivative, after which one returns to the more compact notation to evaluate the outcome.

With these definitions, the basic dynamical quantities of relativistic mechanics and electrodynamics are now expressed in the biquaternion formalism, ready for use in subsequent derivations.

2.6 The EM field in our language

If we apply the matrix multiplication rules to the electromagnetic field with four derivative ∂ and four potential A , with $\partial_0 = -\frac{1}{c}\partial_t$ and $A_0 = \frac{1}{c}\phi$, we get $B = \partial^T A$ as

$$B = \partial^T A = \left(-\frac{1}{c^2}\partial_t\phi - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}\right)\hat{\mathbf{1}} + (\nabla \times \mathbf{A}) \cdot \mathbf{K} + \frac{1}{c}(-\partial_t\mathbf{A} - \nabla\phi) \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}. \quad (42)$$

If we apply the Lorenz gauge $\mathbb{B}_0 = -\frac{1}{c^2}\partial_t\phi - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = 0$ and the usual EM definitions of the fields in terms of the potentials we get

$$B = \partial^T A = \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{K} + \frac{1}{c}\mathbf{E} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}. \quad (43)$$

Using $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\mathbf{K} = -\mathbf{i}\mathbf{K}$, this can also be written as

$$B = \partial^T A = (\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{i}\frac{1}{c}\mathbf{E}) \cdot \mathbf{K} = \overrightarrow{\mathbb{B}} \cdot \mathbf{K}. \quad (44)$$

The use of $\mathbb{B} = \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{i}\frac{1}{c}\mathbf{E}$ dates back to Minkowski's 1908 treatment of the subject [15]. In my opinion, the flexibility of easy switching between the different modes of notations makes my biquaternion variant suited for unification purposes.

Using \mathbb{B} we can write B as

$$B = \mathbb{B}_1\hat{\mathbf{1}} + \mathbb{B}_2\hat{\mathbf{J}} + \mathbb{B}_3\hat{\mathbf{K}} = \overrightarrow{\mathbb{B}} \cdot \mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{i}\mathbb{B}_1 & \mathbb{B}_2 + \mathbf{i}\mathbb{B}_3 \\ -\mathbb{B}_2 + \mathbf{i}\mathbb{B}_3 & -\mathbf{i}\mathbb{B}_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{00} & B_{01} \\ B_{10} & B_{11} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (45)$$

Here $\mathbb{B} := \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{i}\mathbf{E}/c$ is Minkowski's complex field 3-vector; its longitudinal component (parallel to the boost) is invariant, while the transverse pair mixes hyperbolically, as elaborated in the next paragraph.

For the Lorentz transformation of B we can apply the result of the previous section to get $B^L = (\partial^L)^T A^L = (\partial^T)^{L^{-1}} A^L = U(\partial^T)UU^{-1}AU^{-1} = U(\partial^T A)U^{-1} = UBU^{-1}$ for boosts along $\hat{\mathbf{1}}$, so

$$B^L = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\frac{\psi}{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-\frac{\psi}{2}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} B_{00} & B_{01} \\ B_{10} & B_{11} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e^{-\frac{\psi}{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\frac{\psi}{2}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{00} & B_{01}e^{\psi} \\ B_{10}e^{-\psi} & B_{11} \end{bmatrix} \quad (46)$$

which, when written out with \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} leads to the usual result for the Lorentz transformation of the EM field with the Lorentz velocity in the x -direction. But it can also be written as a transformation of the basis, while leaving the coordinates invariant:

$$B^L = UBU^{-1} = \mathbb{B}_1U\hat{\mathbf{1}}U^{-1} + \mathbb{B}_2U\hat{\mathbf{J}}U^{-1} + \mathbb{B}_3U\hat{\mathbf{K}}U^{-1} = \mathbb{B}_1\hat{\mathbf{1}} + \mathbb{B}_2\hat{\mathbf{J}}^L + \mathbb{B}_3\hat{\mathbf{K}}^L = \mathbb{B}_1 \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{i} & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathbf{i} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbb{B}_2 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & e^{\psi} \\ -e^{-\psi} & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \mathbb{B}_3 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{i}e^{\psi} \\ \mathbf{i}e^{-\psi} & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (47)$$

(Since U is diagonal, $U\hat{\mathbf{J}}U^{-1}$ and $U\hat{\mathbf{K}}U^{-1}$ acquire the factors $e^{\pm\psi}$, whereas $U\hat{\mathbf{I}}U^{-1} = \hat{\mathbf{I}}$.) The Lorentz transformation of the EM field can be performed by internally twisting the $(\hat{\mathbf{J}}, \hat{\mathbf{K}})$ -surface perpendicular to the Lorentz velocity and in the process leaving the EM-coordinates invariant.

That the above equals the usual Lorentz transformation of the EM field can be shown by going back to [15], where he wrote the transformation in a form equivalent to

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{B}'_1 \\ \mathbb{B}'_2 \\ \mathbb{B}'_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma & \mathbf{i}\beta\gamma \\ 0 & -\mathbf{i}\beta\gamma & \gamma \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{B}_1 \\ \mathbb{B}_2 \\ \mathbb{B}_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{B}_1 \\ \gamma\mathbb{B}_2 + \mathbf{i}\beta\gamma\mathbb{B}_3 \\ \gamma\mathbb{B}_3 - \mathbf{i}\beta\gamma\mathbb{B}_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (48)$$

So we have

$$B'_{01} = \mathbb{B}'_2 + \mathbf{i}\mathbb{B}'_3 = \gamma\mathbb{B}_2 + \mathbf{i}\beta\gamma\mathbb{B}_3 + \mathbf{i}\gamma\mathbb{B}_3 + \beta\gamma\mathbb{B}_2 \quad (49)$$

and

$$B'_{10} = -\mathbb{B}'_2 + \mathbf{i}\mathbb{B}'_3 = -\gamma\mathbb{B}_2 - \mathbf{i}\beta\gamma\mathbb{B}_3 + \mathbf{i}\gamma\mathbb{B}_3 + \beta\gamma\mathbb{B}_2. \quad (50)$$

If we use the rapidity ψ as $e^\psi = \cosh \psi + \sinh \psi = \gamma + \beta\gamma$, this can be rewritten as

$$B'_{01} = \mathbb{B}'_2 + \mathbf{i}\mathbb{B}'_3 = (\gamma + \beta\gamma)(\mathbb{B}_2 + \mathbf{i}\mathbb{B}_3) = B_{01}e^\psi \quad (51)$$

and

$$B'_{10} = -\mathbb{B}'_2 + \mathbf{i}\mathbb{B}'_3 = (\gamma - \beta\gamma)(-\mathbb{B}_2 + \mathbf{i}\mathbb{B}_3) = B_{10}e^{-\psi}, \quad (52)$$

which leads to Eqn. (46).

2.7 The Maxwell Equations and the Lorentz force law

We start with presenting the Maxwell equations in the developed formalism and then give the Lorentz force law in the same formalism. The Maxwell equations in our language can be given as $\partial B = \mu_0 J$, using $J = \rho V$. Maxwell's inhomogeneous wave equations can be written as $(-\partial^T \partial)B = -\mu_0 \partial^T J$ and with the Lorentz invariant quadratic derivative,

$$-\partial^T \partial = (\nabla^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t^2) \hat{\mathbf{I}} \quad (53)$$

we get the homogeneous wave equations of the EM field in free space in the familiar form as

$$(-\partial^T \partial)B = \nabla^2 B - \frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t^2 B = 0. \quad (54)$$

I will look at $\partial B = \mu_0 J$ first. The underlying structure then also applies to the Lorentz Force Law and the inhomogeneous part of the wave equation. I start with

$$B = \partial^T A = \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{K} + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{E} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}. \quad (55)$$

Then ∂B is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \partial B = & \left(-\frac{1}{c} \partial_t \hat{\mathbf{T}} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{K} \right) \left(\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{K} + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{E} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \right) = \\ & -(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B}) \hat{\mathbf{1}} + \frac{1}{c} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}) \hat{\mathbf{T}} + (\nabla \times \mathbf{B} - \frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t \mathbf{E}) \cdot \mathbf{K} + \frac{1}{c} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E} + \partial_t \mathbf{B}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

If we interpret this result using the knowledge regarding the inhomogeneous Maxwell equations, we get an interesting result. First of all, the part of the Maxwell Equation with the dimension of the norm $\hat{\mathbf{1}}$ is zero and so is the part in the spin-norm sector ($\boldsymbol{\sigma}$). The space-time parts \mathbf{K} and $\hat{\mathbf{T}}$ equal the space-time parts of the four current density J . In the following, ρ denotes charge density for the current density four-vectors, while q denotes single-particle charge. So we get

$$\begin{aligned} \partial B = & -(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B}) \hat{\mathbf{1}} + \frac{1}{c} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}) \hat{\mathbf{T}} + (\nabla \times \mathbf{B} - \frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t \mathbf{E}) \cdot \mathbf{K} + \frac{1}{c} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E} + \partial_t \mathbf{B}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \\ & 0 \hat{\mathbf{1}} + \mu_0 c \rho \hat{\mathbf{T}} + \mu_0 \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{K} + 0 \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mu_0 J. \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

So the spin-norm part of the Maxwell Equations equals zero and the space-time part equals the space-time four current density times μ_0 . In the line of this interpretation, magnetic monopoles and the correlated magnetic monopole current should be searched in the pauliquat dimensions of spin-norm, not in the minquat dimensions of space-time.

As for the Lorentz covariance of the Maxwell Equations, this can be demonstrated quite easily. Given the four-vectors ∂ , A and J in reference system S_1 , with the Maxwell Equations as $\partial(\partial^T A) = \mu_0 J$, then in reference system S_2 we have the four-vectors ∂^L , A^L and J^L and the covariant Maxwell Equations given as $\partial^L(\partial^L)^T A^L = \mu_0 J^L$. In S_2 this can be proven through

$$\begin{aligned} \partial^L(\partial^L)^T A^L = & \partial^L(\partial^T)^{L^{-1}} A^L = U^{-1} \partial U^{-1} U(\partial^T) U U^{-1} A U^{-1} = U^{-1} \partial(\partial^T) A U^{-1} = \\ & U^{-1} \partial B U^{-1} = U^{-1} \mu_0 J U^{-1} = \mu_0 J^L. \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

So if we have $\partial B = \mu_0 J$ in one frame of reference, this transforms as $\partial^L B^L = \mu_0 J^L$ in another frame of reference, which means that the equation maintains its form, it is Lorentz covariant. We have form-invariance of the equations.

I will look at $JB = F$ now, with $J = qV$. The underlying structure for the Lorentz Force Law is the same as for the Maxwell equations. So JB is given by

$$\begin{aligned} JB = & \left(cq \hat{\mathbf{T}} + \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{K} \right) \left(\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{K} + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{E} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \right) = \\ & -(\mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{B}) \hat{\mathbf{1}} + \frac{1}{c} (\mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{E}) \hat{\mathbf{T}} + (\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B} + q\mathbf{E}) \cdot \mathbf{K} + \left(\frac{1}{c} \mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{E} - cq\mathbf{B} \right) \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

If we interpret this result using the knowledge regarding the Lorentz Force Law, we get an interesting result. First of all, the part of the Lorentz force law with the dimension of the norm $\hat{\mathbf{1}}$ is zero and so is the part in the spin-norm sector (σ). The space-time parts \mathbf{K} and $\hat{\mathbf{T}}$ equal the space-time parts of the four force F . Thus we get

$$JB = -(\mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{B})\hat{\mathbf{1}} + \frac{1}{c}(\mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{E})\hat{\mathbf{T}} + (\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B} + q\mathbf{E}) \cdot \mathbf{K} + \left(\frac{1}{c}\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{E} - cq\mathbf{B}\right) \cdot \sigma =$$

$$0\hat{\mathbf{1}} + \frac{1}{c}P\hat{\mathbf{T}} + F \cdot \mathbf{K} + 0\sigma = F. \quad (60)$$

So the spin-norm pauliquat part of the Lorentz Force Law equals zero and the space-time minquat part equals the space-time four force.

In both cases, ∂B and BJ , we get a dual spin-norm and space-time product, with the spin-norm equal zero and the non-zero space-time leading to the inhomogeneous four-vectors of current and force. Speculations about magnetic monopoles are connected to these spin-norm parts, the set spanned by pauliquats. In my analysis, if spin-norm is the twin dual of space-time and as such an integral aspect of the metric as foreseen in [16], then searches for magnetic monopoles should focus on this spin-norm aspect of the vacuum.

But from a purely geometric perspective, the product of three four-vectors like in $BJ = \partial^T AJ = F$, we can separate the coordinate four sets ∂_μ , A^ν , and J^μ from the metric basis, as in $BJ = ((\partial_\mu A^\nu)J^\mu)((\mathbf{K}_\mu^T \mathbf{K}^\nu) \mathbf{K}^\mu)$, and focus on the metric product alone. We then get

$$\mathbf{K}_\mu{}^\nu \mathbf{K}^\mu = (\mathbf{K}_\mu^T \mathbf{K}^\nu) \mathbf{K}^\mu = \begin{bmatrix} -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{T}} & \hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{I}} & \hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{I}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{I}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{J}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{K}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} & \hat{\mathbf{J}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} & \hat{\mathbf{K}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{T}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{I}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{J}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{K}} \end{bmatrix} = \quad (61)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{T}} + \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{I}} + \hat{\mathbf{J}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} + \hat{\mathbf{K}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{I}} + \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{I}} + \hat{\mathbf{J}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} + \hat{\mathbf{K}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} + \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} + \hat{\mathbf{J}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{J}} + \hat{\mathbf{K}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} + \hat{\mathbf{I}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} + \hat{\mathbf{J}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} + \hat{\mathbf{K}}\hat{\mathbf{T}}\hat{\mathbf{K}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{T}} - \hat{\mathbf{T}} - \hat{\mathbf{T}} - \hat{\mathbf{T}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{I}} - \hat{\mathbf{I}} + \hat{\mathbf{I}} + \hat{\mathbf{I}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{J}} + \hat{\mathbf{J}} - \hat{\mathbf{J}} + \hat{\mathbf{J}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{K}} + \hat{\mathbf{K}} + \hat{\mathbf{K}} - \hat{\mathbf{K}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (62)$$

with no norm-spin ($\hat{\mathbf{1}}, \sigma$) product in the end result: only pure ($\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \mathbf{K}$) components remain. The product of three four-vectors in this metric/geometry environment should produce a space-time four-vector only, as is reflected in the Maxwell equations and the Lorentz Force Law. In other words, the multiplication of three minquats produces a pure minquat, not a pauliquat or a sum of a pauliquat and a minquat. In this formalism, the metric analysis excludes non-zero ($\hat{\mathbf{1}}, \sigma$) contributions from these products, which suggests that monopole-like sources cannot be represented within this framework.

3 The Dirac spin level

3.1 The Dirac–Weyl environment and its disconnect from Minkowski space-time

In the 1920s the quadratic relativistic Klein–Gordon wave equation was found inadequate for describing the relativistic electron with intrinsic (Pauli) spin. In his search for a solution, Dirac linearized the Klein–Gordon equation by introducing 4×4 matrices built as duplexes of the 2×2 Pauli matrices. In his two seminal 1928 papers he introduced the Clifford four-set (β, α) and, using what were later called the gamma matrices, the covariant Clifford four-set (β, γ) [17, 18]. The Pauli matrices were embedded within these structures. Shortly thereafter Weyl introduced an alternative covariant Clifford four-set, related to Dirac’s by the distinction between low-velocity and high-velocity relativistic regimes [19]. Weyl also explicitly analyzed parity P and time-reversal T properties of these representations [20, 21].

All such gamma or gamma-like matrices can be represented in terms of 2×2 matrices over the biquaternion Pauli basis $(\hat{\mathbf{I}}, \sigma)$. However, using this basis highlights the difficulty of connecting the gamma four-vector—defined in an abstract Dirac spinor space—to the Minkowski four-vectors of special relativity. Once spinor wave functions are introduced to form a Hilbert space, the gap between the abstract representation and Minkowski space-time becomes even more pronounced. The Born rule provides an operational link between spinor amplitudes and experimental probabilities, but it does not in itself restore a direct geometric connection to Minkowski space-time.

Using the results of the previous section, however, we can build gamma-equivalent matrices with an explicit connection to Minkowski space-time. In particular, the biquaternion minquat basis $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \mathbf{K})$ offers a direct bridge between the Clifford algebra of relativistic quantum mechanics and the space-time of special relativity. Establishing the Dirac environment on this basis may provide a fruitful and insightful foundation for unifying the two descriptions.

In the next subsection we will construct the gamma matrices explicitly in terms of $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \mathbf{K})$, showing how the Dirac equation can be derived directly from this space-time based formalism. A key advantage of this approach is that Lorentz covariance is derived constructively rather than assumed. The transformation properties of the basis elements $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \mathbf{K})$, established earlier (Lemma 1), ensure that the gamma-equivalent matrices built from them satisfy the correct Clifford algebra relations and inherit the proper Lorentz behavior. In this way, the Dirac equation and its Lorentz transformation can be connected directly to Minkowski space-time through construction rather than through postulate.

3.2 The Weyl matrices in dual minquat space-time mode as beta matrices.

In my mathematical–physical language and with a block-doubling construction (analogous to a Möbius transform in form) in mind I can define matrices through the application of parity or point reflection P and time reversal or time reversal T of the energy-momentum four-vector P as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \begin{bmatrix} P & P \\ P^P & P^T \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} P & P \\ -P^T & P^T \end{bmatrix} = \\
 p_0 & \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{T}} & \hat{\mathbf{T}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{T}} & -\hat{\mathbf{T}} \end{bmatrix} + p_1 \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{I}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{I}} & \hat{\mathbf{I}} \end{bmatrix} + p_2 \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{J}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{J}} & \hat{\mathbf{J}} \end{bmatrix} + p_3 \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{K}} & \hat{\mathbf{K}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{K}} & \hat{\mathbf{K}} \end{bmatrix} = \\
 & p_0 \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{T}} & \hat{\mathbf{T}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{T}} & -\hat{\mathbf{T}} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K} & \mathbf{K} \\ -\mathbf{K} & \mathbf{K} \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

The problem with this matrix is that it doesn't represent a Clifford four-set.

I can split the quadruple of P into two duplexes $P_\mu\beta^\mu + P_\mu\xi^\mu$. The beta's are defined through, constructed as, the parity duplex

$$\begin{aligned}
 \not{P} = P_\mu\beta^\mu &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & P \\ -P^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} = p_0 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \hat{\mathbf{T}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{T}} & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{K} \\ -\mathbf{K} & 0 \end{bmatrix} = p_0\beta_0 + \mathbf{p} \cdot \boldsymbol{\beta} = \\
 & p_0 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \hat{\mathbf{T}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{T}} & 0 \end{bmatrix} + p_1 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \hat{\mathbf{I}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{I}} & 0 \end{bmatrix} + p_2 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \hat{\mathbf{J}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{J}} & 0 \end{bmatrix} + p_3 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \hat{\mathbf{K}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{K}} & 0 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

with $\not{P} = P_\mu\beta^\mu = p_0\beta_0 + p_1\beta_1 + p_2\beta_2 + p_3\beta_3$.

The xi's are defined through, constructed as, the time reversed duplex

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_\mu\xi^\mu &= \begin{bmatrix} P & 0 \\ 0 & P^T \end{bmatrix} = p_0 \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{T}} & 0 \\ 0 & -\hat{\mathbf{T}} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{K} \end{bmatrix} = p_0\xi_0 + \mathbf{p} \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi} = \\
 & p_0 \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{T}} & 0 \\ 0 & -\hat{\mathbf{T}} \end{bmatrix} + p_1 \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{I}} & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{\mathbf{I}} \end{bmatrix} + p_2 \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{J}} & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{\mathbf{J}} \end{bmatrix} + p_3 \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{K}} & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{\mathbf{K}} \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{65}$$

with $P_\mu\xi^\mu = p_0\xi_0 + p_1\xi_1 + p_2\xi_2 + p_3\xi_3$.

The relation with the metric of the previous section is direct. In the β_μ case space is mirrored, so the space-time double arises through the parity operation. In the ξ_μ time is reversed, so the space-time double is obtained through the T operation.

Of these two constructions, only the β_μ matrices form a Clifford four-set: their products satisfy $\{\beta_\mu, \beta_\nu\} = 2\eta_{\mu\nu} \mathbb{1}$.^{6,7} By contrast, the ξ_μ matrices fail to satisfy

⁶ Here, $\mathbb{1}$ is the 4×4 identity matrix, where $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ is the 2×2 identity matrix.

⁷ Explicitly, one verifies $\beta_0^2 = \mathbb{1}$, $\beta_i^2 = -\mathbb{1}$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$), and $\beta_\mu\beta_\nu = -\beta_\nu\beta_\mu$ for $\mu \neq \nu$, so that $\{\beta_\mu, \beta_\nu\} = 2\eta_{\mu\nu} \mathbb{1}$. Thus the β_μ indeed form a Clifford four-set.

the Clifford relations. The β_μ are therefore the natural minquat equivalent of the Weyl γ -matrices, just as those are obtained in the standard approach by doubling the Pauli spin-norm basis. If I use $\hat{\mathbf{T}} = \mathbf{i}\hat{\mathbf{1}}$ and $\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{i}\sigma$, the result is

$$\beta_\mu = (\beta_0, \boldsymbol{\beta}) = \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{i}\hat{\mathbf{1}} \\ \mathbf{i}\hat{\mathbf{1}} & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{i}\sigma \\ -\mathbf{i}\sigma & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) = (\mathbf{i}\hat{\mathbf{1}}, \mathbf{i}\boldsymbol{\gamma}) = \mathbf{i}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_\mu \quad (66)$$

which relates the parity dual β_μ to the Weyl gamma representation. This establishes the Weyl representation in the minquat setting. In the next step we will address how the full Dirac representation (obtained in the standard formalism by doubling the Weyl set) can be realized in the minquat environment.

3.3 From the Weyl and Dirac equations to the Dirac beta matrices

The trick in finding Clifford four-sets is connected to the problem of the quadratics and to the problem of formulating equations in the Dirac environment. The quadratics of the energy-momentum four-vectors in the Clifford representation have to be reducible to the Klein Gordon energy condition $P^T P = E^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}}$ with $E = \frac{U_0}{c} = m_0 c$. The Weyl beta representation of \not{P} matches this requirement. The ξ_μ representation doesn't.

In order to linearize the Klein–Gordon condition, we introduce an energy operator in block-matrix form. The scalar relation $P^T P = E^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}}$ corresponds in the Weyl setting to the matrix identity

$$\not{P}\not{P} = -E^2 \mathbb{1}.$$

This quadratic can be factorized if we represent the energy through the eigen-time matrix

$$\xi = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{T}} & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{\mathbf{T}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (E\xi)^2 = -E^2 \mathbb{1}.$$

We therefore define

$$\not{E} := E \xi, \quad \not{E}^2 = -E^2 \mathbb{1}.$$

With this construction, the quadratic $\not{P}\not{P} = -E^2 \mathbb{1}$ can be rewritten as $\not{P}\not{P} = \not{E}\not{E}$, which admits the desired linear factorization.

The Weyl or chiral equation stems from the quadratic $\not{P}\not{P} = \not{E}\not{E}$ in the space-time Weyl representation.

$$\begin{aligned} \not{P}\not{P} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & P \\ -P^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & P \\ -P^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -PP^T & 0 \\ 0 & -P^T P \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} -E^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}} & 0 \\ 0 & -E^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}} \end{bmatrix} = -E^2 \mathbb{1} = \not{E}\not{E} \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

From the construction we have

$$\not{P}\not{P} - \not{E}\not{E} = 0,$$

which factorizes as

$$(\not{P} - \not{E})(\not{P} + \not{E}) = 0.$$

If these factors are interpreted as operator equations on their own, $(\not{P} \pm \not{E}) = 0$, the only solutions are trivial unless $m_0 = 0$. This explains why the Weyl equation describes only massless particles such as neutrinos.

To obtain nontrivial solutions when $m_0 \neq 0$, one must enlarge the representation space: the operators $\not{P} \pm \not{E}$ act trivially on numbers, but can act nontrivially on spinors, which serve as the carrier space of the linearized equations. We therefore introduce a wave function Ψ , interpreted as a spinor field. In this setting the quadratic relation is imposed on bilinear forms,

$$\Psi^\dagger (\not{P} - \not{E})(\not{P} + \not{E})\Psi = 0,$$

so that it suffices to require

$$(\not{P} + \not{E})\Psi = 0, \quad \Psi^\dagger (\not{P} - \not{E}) = 0,$$

for nonvanishing Ψ . Here Ψ^\dagger is the Hermitian conjugate row spinor of the column spinor Ψ .

By interpreting spinors as wave-like fields, these equations can be read as eigenvalue conditions for the operators $\not{P} \pm \not{E}$. With $\hat{P} = -i\hbar \not{P}$ we arrive at the Weyl wave equations

$$\Psi^\dagger \hat{P} = \Psi^\dagger \not{E}, \tag{68}$$

$$\hat{P}\Psi = -\not{E}\Psi. \tag{69}$$

For zero rest mass ($m_0 = 0$, hence $E = 0$), these reduce to the familiar massless Weyl equations

$$\Psi^\dagger \hat{P} = 0, \quad \hat{P}\Psi = 0.$$

This analysis shows how the Weyl formalism emerges naturally from the factorization of the quadratic condition and why it is restricted to massless particles. To go beyond and accommodate massive fermions, the construction must be extended: by enlarging the representation space and mixing the parity and time-reversal duplexes, one arrives at the Dirac equation in its full form.

Unlike in the Weyl case, where the algebra alone suffices to describe massless fields, the Dirac case necessarily requires the introduction of spinors. Without them, the factorization of the quadratic condition would again reduce to trivial

solutions. To describe massive fermions such as the electron, we must therefore enlarge the representation space so that nontrivial solutions exist when $m_0 \neq 0$. This enlargement is achieved by mixing the parity and time-reversal duplexes, leading to the Dirac representation. In this setting the quadratic condition becomes

$$\not{P}\not{P} = (p_0\beta_0 + \mathbf{p} \cdot \boldsymbol{\beta})^2 = -E^2\mathbb{1},$$

with explicit block form

$$\not{P}\not{P} = \begin{bmatrix} p_0\hat{\mathbf{T}} & \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{K} \\ -\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{K} & -p_0\hat{\mathbf{T}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} p_0\hat{\mathbf{T}} & \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{K} \\ -\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{K} & -p_0\hat{\mathbf{T}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (-p_0^2 + \mathbf{p}^2)\hat{\mathbf{I}} & 0 \\ 0 & (-p_0^2 + \mathbf{p}^2)\hat{\mathbf{I}} \end{bmatrix} = -E^2\mathbb{1}.$$

This leads to the two options for the Dirac equations

$$(\hat{p}_0\beta_0 + \hat{\mathbf{p}} \cdot \boldsymbol{\beta})\Psi = E\mathbf{i}\mathbb{1}\Psi \quad (70)$$

$$\Psi^\dagger(\hat{p}_0\beta_0 + \hat{\mathbf{p}} \cdot \boldsymbol{\beta}) = -E\Psi^\dagger\mathbf{i}\mathbb{1} \quad (71)$$

if we use $\hat{P} = -\mathbf{i}\hbar\partial$ and a four column spinor Ψ .

From this we can derive the Dirac beta matrices, i.e. the beta-matrices in the Dirac representation. The Dirac representation mixes the beta and the xi representation, so that the temporal part is doubled via ξ , while the spatial parts retain the β structure. This representation thus represents a PT dual, because the Dirac block form uses beta for the spatial parts and xi for the temporal part. I nevertheless, using the gamma tradition, use the beta and Feynman slash symbols for both representations in the time-space $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \mathbf{K})$ basis. This gives for the Dirac beta representation

$$\begin{aligned} \not{P} &= P_\mu\beta^\mu = p_0 \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{T}} & 0 \\ 0 & -\hat{\mathbf{T}} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{K} \\ -\mathbf{K} & 0 \end{bmatrix} = p_0\beta_0 + \mathbf{p} \cdot \boldsymbol{\beta} = \\ & p_0 \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{T}} & 0 \\ 0 & -\hat{\mathbf{T}} \end{bmatrix} + p_1 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \hat{\mathbf{I}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{I}} & 0 \end{bmatrix} + p_2 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \hat{\mathbf{J}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{J}} & 0 \end{bmatrix} + p_3 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \hat{\mathbf{K}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{K}} & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (72)$$

Both the Weyl and Dirac block constructions yield Clifford sets equivalent to the usual gamma matrices, up to the factor of \mathbf{i} : $\beta_\mu = \mathbf{i}\gamma_\mu$.

So in the space-time representation we have the Weyl \not{P} as

$$\not{P}_w = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & P \\ -P^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (73)$$

and the Dirac \not{P} as

$$\not{P}_d = \begin{bmatrix} p_0\hat{\mathbf{T}} & \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{K} \\ -\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{K} & -p_0\hat{\mathbf{T}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (74)$$

3.3.1 The transformation from the Dirac to the Weyl representation and vice versa

A key step in connecting the Weyl and Dirac representations is the similarity transformation S . While this operator is well known in the standard formalism, in the present framework it acquires a central role: it is the explicit bridge that allows us to move between the Weyl and Dirac β -representations constructed above, and it will serve as the core mechanism for establishing Lorentz covariance of the Dirac equation by construction rather than postulate.

Given the Weyl and Dirac β representations of Eqn. (73) and Eqn. (74), the transformation matrix can be written in one of its usual forms as

$$S = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{1}} & \hat{\mathbf{1}} \\ -\hat{\mathbf{1}} & \hat{\mathbf{1}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (75)$$

It has the property $\beta_0 S = S^{-1} \beta_0$, and equivalently $S \beta_0 = \beta_0 S^{-1}$.

The switch from the Weyl β_w^v to the Dirac β_d^v is then given by $\beta_d^v = S \beta_w^v S^{-1}$, and the reverse by $\beta_w^v = S^{-1} \beta_d^v S$. We then also have the transformations $\not{P}_w = S^{-1} \not{P}_d S$ and $\not{P}_d = S \not{P}_w S^{-1}$.

This similarity transformation S will play a central role in the next section, where it provides the constructive mechanism for demonstrating the Lorentz covariance of the Dirac equation within the present framework.

3.4 Lorentz transformations of the vectors in the Dirac and Weyl representation environments

In the Pauli level part of this paper I developed the $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}, \mathbf{K})$ relativistic approach. This resulted in the Lorentz transformation of a four-vector $P = (p_0 \hat{\mathbf{T}}, \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{K})$ as $P^L = U^{-1} P U^{-1}$ and the Lorentz transformation of its time reversal P^T as $(P^L)^T = (P^T)^{L^{-1}} = U P^T U$ with U as

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\frac{\psi}{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-\frac{\psi}{2}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (76)$$

and the rapidity ψ . The quadratic $P^T P$ is a Lorentz invariant scalar $\frac{U_0^2}{c^2} \hat{\mathbf{1}} = E^2 \hat{\mathbf{1}}$ with the dimension of the norm $\hat{\mathbf{1}}$. If in the space-time minquat β_μ representation we have the Weyl \not{P} in a reference system S as

$$\not{P} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & P \\ -P^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (77)$$

then in reference system S' we have P^L and so also the Weyl \not{P}^L as

$$\not{P}^L = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & P^L \\ -(P^L)^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & U^{-1} P U^{-1} \\ -U P^T U & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (78)$$

The question then is which matrix can generate this result. The obvious answer is

$$\mathbb{P}_w^L = \Lambda_W \mathbb{P}_w \Lambda_W^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} U^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & U \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & P \\ -P^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U & 0 \\ 0 & U^{-1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & U^{-1} P U^{-1} \\ -U P^T U & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (79)$$

with the Lorentz transformation matrix

$$\Lambda_W = \begin{bmatrix} U^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & U \end{bmatrix} \quad (80)$$

and its inverse Λ_W^{-1} .

As for the generator of Λ_W , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_W = \begin{bmatrix} U^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & U \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} e^{-\frac{\psi}{2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\frac{\psi}{2}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{\frac{\psi}{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & e^{-\frac{\psi}{2}} \end{bmatrix} = \\ & \begin{bmatrix} \cosh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cosh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cosh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cosh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) \end{bmatrix} + \\ & \begin{bmatrix} -\sinh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sinh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sinh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\sinh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) \end{bmatrix} = \\ & \cosh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{1}} & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{\mathbf{1}} \end{bmatrix} + \sinh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) \begin{bmatrix} -\sigma_I & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_I \end{bmatrix} = \\ & \mathbb{1} \cosh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) + \alpha_I \sinh\left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right) = \mathbb{1} e^{\alpha_I \left(\frac{\psi}{2}\right)}. \quad (81) \end{aligned}$$

The α_I is defined in the Weyl presentation as:

$$\alpha_I = \begin{bmatrix} -\sigma_I & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_I \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (82)$$

and this ensures $\alpha_I^2 = \mathbb{1}$. The inverse of Λ_W is then obviously given by $\Lambda_W^{-1} = \mathbb{1} e^{-\alpha_I(\frac{\psi}{2})}$. These expressions hold for boosts aligned with $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ (our x-axis). Generic boosts are obtained by a spatial rotation to align with $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$, apply the formulas, then rotate back.

The Klein Gordon energy-momentum condition's Lorentz invariance or covariance depends on the product $\not{P}^L \not{P}^L$. Using the previous result, we have for the Lorentz transformation of the product $\not{P} \not{P}$ in the Weyl representation

$$\begin{aligned} \not{P}^L \not{P}^L &= \Lambda_W \not{P} \Lambda_W^{-1} \Lambda_W \not{P} \Lambda_W^{-1} = \Lambda_W \not{P} \not{P} \Lambda_W^{-1} = \\ &= \Lambda_W (-E^2 \mathbb{1}) \Lambda_W^{-1} = -E^2 \mathbb{1} \Lambda_W \Lambda_W^{-1} = -E^2 \mathbb{1} = \not{P} \not{P}, \end{aligned} \quad (83)$$

so a Lorentz invariant product. This ensures the Lorentz invariance of the Klein Gordon energy-momentum condition $\not{P} \not{P} = \not{E} \not{E}$ in the Weyl representation.

In the Dirac version, where $\not{P} = p_0 \beta_0 + \mathbf{p} \cdot \boldsymbol{\beta}$, things get more complicated. We have to start with the Dirac \not{P}_d in the primary reference system and we want to end up with \not{P}_d^L in the secondary reference system. We know how to transform between the Dirac and the Weyl representations and we know how to Lorentz transform the Weyl \not{P}_w . This means we have to go from Dirac to Weyl in the primary reference system, then Lorentz transform the Weyl four-vector to the secondary reference system and then transform back from the Weyl to the Dirac representation, three operations in total. The total result gives

$$\not{P}_d^L = S \Lambda_W S^{-1} \not{P}_d S \Lambda_W^{-1} S^{-1}. \quad (84)$$

In the Dirac representation,

$$\not{P}_d^L = S \Lambda_W S^{-1} \not{P}_d S \Lambda_W^{-1} S^{-1}, \quad \Lambda_D := S \Lambda_W S^{-1}, \quad \Lambda_D^{-1} := S \Lambda_W^{-1} S^{-1}.$$

Then

$$\not{P}_d^L \not{P}_d^L = \Lambda_D \not{P}_d \Lambda_D^{-1} \Lambda_D \not{P}_d \Lambda_D^{-1} = \Lambda_D (\not{P}_d^2) \Lambda_D^{-1} = \Lambda_D (-E^2 \mathbb{1}) \Lambda_D^{-1} = -E^2 \mathbb{1},$$

so the Klein–Gordon condition remains Lorentz invariant.

In details, with rapidity ψ , the operator $\Lambda_D = S \Lambda S^{-1}$ is given as

$$\Lambda_D = \begin{bmatrix} \cosh(\frac{\psi}{2}) \hat{\mathbf{I}} & \sinh(\frac{\psi}{2}) \sigma_I \\ \sinh(\frac{\psi}{2}) \sigma_I & \cosh(\frac{\psi}{2}) \hat{\mathbf{I}} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbb{1} \cosh(\frac{\psi}{2}) + \alpha_I \sinh(\frac{\psi}{2}) = \mathbb{1} e^{(\alpha_I \frac{\psi}{2})}, \quad (85)$$

with $\mathbb{1} e^{(\alpha_I \frac{\psi}{2})}$ as the generator of the Lorentz boost. The α_I in the Dirac representation is defined as:

$$\alpha_I = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \sigma_I \\ \sigma_I & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (86)$$

The operator $\Lambda_D^{-1} = S\Lambda_W^{-1}S^{-1}$ is given as

$$\Lambda_D^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \cosh(\frac{\psi}{2})\hat{\mathbf{1}} & -\sinh(\frac{\psi}{2})\sigma_I \\ -\sinh(\frac{\psi}{2})\sigma_I & \cosh(\frac{\psi}{2})\hat{\mathbf{1}} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbb{1} \cosh(\frac{\psi}{2}) - \alpha_I \sinh(\frac{\psi}{2}) = \mathbb{1} e^{-(\alpha_I \frac{\psi}{2})}. \quad (87)$$

In the transformation of the four-vector we have $\not{P}_d = P_\mu \beta^\mu$. Because the operators only work on the matrix aspect of each of the elements of β^μ , the Lorentz transformation can also be written as

$$\not{P}^L = e^{(\alpha_I \frac{\psi}{2})} \not{P} e^{-(\alpha_I \frac{\psi}{2})} = \Lambda_D P_\mu \beta^\mu \Lambda_D^{-1} = P_\mu \Lambda_D \beta^\mu \Lambda_D^{-1} \quad (88)$$

and we can focus on

$$(\beta^\mu)^L = \Lambda_D \beta^\mu \Lambda_D^{-1} \quad (89)$$

thus interpreting the Lorentz transformation as a boost of the dual minquat metric.

Using the Lorentz transformation expression of the operator combinations Λ_D and Λ_D^{-1} in terms of the rapidity and the hyperbolic trigonometric expressions, we can calculate the result on the beta matrices of the Λ_D and Λ_D^{-1} operators. After some calculations this results in

$$\boxed{\Lambda_D \beta^\mu \Lambda_D^{-1} = \Lambda_\nu{}^\mu \beta^\nu} \quad (90)$$

with, given the usual Lorentz boost $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}$ and $\beta = \frac{v}{c}$,

$$(\beta^\mu)^L = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_0 \\ \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \\ \beta_3 \end{bmatrix}^L = \Lambda_\nu{}^\mu \beta^\nu = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma & -\gamma\beta & 0 & 0 \\ -\gamma\beta & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \beta_0 \\ \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \\ \beta_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma\beta_0 - \beta\gamma\beta_1 \\ \gamma\beta_1 - \beta\gamma\beta_0 \\ \beta_2 \\ \beta_3 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (91)$$

Independently from the previous direct calculations based on known Λ_D , S and $\Lambda_\nu{}^\mu$, the Lorentz transformation of P can also be presented as a transformation of the coordinates P_μ with a fixed metric K^μ , see the results of Eqn.(27). For the beta dual this applies as well. Thus one either transforms the coordinates P_μ or one transforms the metric in β^μ , but not both. The end result will be the same. For the first we get

$$\not{P}^L = (P_\mu \beta^\mu)^L = (P_\mu)^L \beta^\mu = (P_\nu \Lambda_\mu{}^\nu) \beta^\mu = P'_\mu \beta^\mu. \quad (92)$$

But this can also be written as

$$\not{P}^L = (P_\nu \Lambda_\mu^\nu) \beta^\mu = P_\nu (\Lambda_\mu^\nu \beta^\mu) = P_\nu \beta^{\nu'}. \quad (93)$$

So we have $(\beta^\nu)^L = \Lambda_\mu^\nu \beta^\mu$. This is the precise sense in which the β^ν transform as a 4-vector basis under boosts, complementing the dual picture where one holds the basis fixed and transforms P_μ . And we have, in the Dirac representation, $(\beta^\nu)^L = \Lambda_D \beta^\nu \Lambda_D^{-1}$, leading to

$$\Lambda_\mu^\nu \beta^\mu = \Lambda_D \beta^\nu \Lambda_D^{-1}. \quad (94)$$

In the space-time Weyl representation the results are the same, giving

$$\Lambda_W \beta^\mu \Lambda_W^{-1} = \Lambda_\mu^\nu \beta^\mu. \quad (95)$$

A remark is necessary: one has to keep track of the representation one is in, Weyl or Dirac, because the same Λ_μ^ν and β^μ symbols are used but they aren't equal in the respective representations.

The ease of the Lorentz transformation and the proving of Lorentz covariance or invariance in the developed math-phys environment can be contrasted with the usual approach as critically analyzed and alternatively presented in [8]. The relation $\Lambda_D \beta^\mu \Lambda_D^{-1} = \Lambda_\mu^\nu \beta^\mu$ for the Dirac matrices in this paper has been constructed using already known matrices. I do not use this relationship as a starting point in the process of finding the operator Λ_D , as is done in the literature. As I mentioned in the introduction, in [5, p. 147, Eqn. 5.102], the Λ_D is a black box, whereas in my approach I opened the box and found $\Lambda_D = S \Lambda_W S^{-1}$, a relation that I constructed and then used to prove $\Lambda_D \beta^\mu \Lambda_D^{-1} = \Lambda_\mu^\nu \beta^\mu$ instead of assuming it first and solving it later. I do not assume and solve, I construct and prove instead. This was possible because of its connection to the Lorentz transformation approach in the biquaternion representation of the Pauli level physics. Thus the covariance of the Dirac equation is not assumed but emerges from the geometric structure established at the Pauli level.

My approach confirms the claim that the beta matrices can transform like a 'regular' four-vector, but it also confirms the approach that the beta matrices remain fixed during a Lorentz transformation. One has to realize that in the Feynman $\not{P} = P_\mu \beta^\mu$ notation, the Lorentz transformation is either performed on P_μ with fixed β^μ or on β^μ with fixed P_μ : one either transforms the coordinates or one transforms the metric, but not both. Either the metric aspect of \not{P} is Doppler twisted or the dynamic variables are, but not both.

3.5 Lorentz transformations of the spinors in the Weyl representation environments

The Lorentz transformation of the spinors is known to be half the Lorentz transformation of a four-vector. In case of the Weyl beta representation we have $\not{P}^L = \Lambda \not{P} \Lambda^{-1}$, so we expect to have either $\Psi^L = \Lambda \Psi$ or $\Psi^L = \Lambda^{-1} \Psi$.

Now, in physics, the Lorentz transformation of EM-waves represents a relativistic Doppler boost, represented by the factor $e^\psi = \gamma + \gamma\beta$ shifting the frequency and wavelength to the red or to the blue. Matter waves and the associated phenomena are duly called so because they exhibit wave phenomena as refraction and interference. So matter waves should have wave-fronts and crests and troughs and as such undergo the equivalent of Doppler shifts when observed from $v\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ -boosted reference systems. But measurements always involve intensities, never pure waves, so the intensities should exhibit quantum Doppler shifts.

We further know that if the spinor Ψ represents a matter wave, then $\Theta = \not{P}\Psi$ also represents a matter wave and both should Lorentz transform identically. From this we can infer that $\Psi^L = \Lambda\Psi$, because then

$$\Theta^L = (\not{P}\Psi)^L = \not{P}^L \Psi^L = \Lambda \not{P} \Lambda^{-1} \Psi^L = \Lambda \not{P} \Lambda^{-1} \Lambda \Psi = \Lambda \not{P} \Psi = \Lambda \Theta \quad (96)$$

From $\Psi^L = \Lambda\Psi$ we can derive the relation

$$(\Psi^L)^\dagger = (\Lambda\Psi)^\dagger = \Psi^\dagger \Lambda, \quad (97)$$

due to the fact that Λ is diagonal real and thus equal to its conjugate transpose.

We then get for Lorentz transformation of the intensity $\Psi^\dagger\Psi$ of the matter wave Ψ

$$\begin{aligned} (\Psi^\dagger\Psi)^L &= (\Psi^L)^\dagger(\Psi^L) = (\Lambda\Psi)^\dagger(\Lambda\Psi) = \Psi^\dagger\Lambda\Lambda\Psi = \Psi^\dagger\Lambda^2\Psi = \Psi^\dagger e^{\alpha_I\psi}\Psi = \\ &= \Psi^\dagger\Psi \cosh(\psi) + \Psi^\dagger\alpha_I\Psi \sinh(\psi) = \Psi^\dagger\Psi\gamma + \Psi^\dagger\alpha_I\Psi\gamma\beta, \end{aligned} \quad (98)$$

with alpha matrix α_I , Lorentz boost $\gamma = \cosh(\psi)$, $\gamma\beta = \sinh(\psi)$. This is the quantum equivalent of a Doppler boost with rapidity ψ , as should be expected for a wave phenomenon when observed from a moving reference system.

In the Weyl representation, boosting the probability density doesn't mix the spinors because we have a diagonal matrix in the Lorentz boost operator, as

$$\begin{aligned} (\Psi^\dagger\Psi)^L &= [\Psi_1^* \ \Psi_2^* \ \Psi_3^* \ \Psi_4^*] \begin{bmatrix} \gamma - \gamma\beta & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma + \gamma\beta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma + \gamma\beta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \gamma - \gamma\beta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_1 \\ \Psi_2 \\ \Psi_3 \\ \Psi_4 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \gamma\Psi_1^*\Psi_1 - \gamma\beta\Psi_1^*\Psi_1 + \gamma\Psi_2^*\Psi_2 + \gamma\beta\Psi_2^*\Psi_2 \\ &\quad + \gamma\Psi_3^*\Psi_3 + \gamma\beta\Psi_3^*\Psi_3 + \gamma\Psi_4^*\Psi_4 - \gamma\beta\Psi_4^*\Psi_4 = \\ &= \Psi_1^*\Psi_1 e^{-\psi} + \Psi_2^*\Psi_2 e^\psi + \Psi_3^*\Psi_3 e^\psi + \Psi_4^*\Psi_4 e^{-\psi}. \end{aligned} \quad (99)$$

The factor $\gamma \pm \gamma\beta = e^{\pm\psi}$ represents a relativistic wavelength/frequency Doppler shift of the intensities.

In Wave Mechanics, the equations are wave equations and the Lagrangians are the intensities of those waves. The Klein-Gordon energy-momentum condition is Lorentz Invariant, the linearized Dirac equation transforms like a wave Ψ and the Lagrangian wave intensity derived from that equation transforms Doppler like with a factor $e^{\alpha_I\psi}$.

The condition $\Psi^L = \Lambda\Psi$ gives

$$\Psi_w^L = \Lambda\Psi_w = \begin{bmatrix} U^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & U \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_w^1 \\ \Psi_w^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} U^{-1}\Psi_w^1 \\ U\Psi_w^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (100)$$

In this Weyl space–time representation the two bispinors Ψ_w^1 and Ψ_w^2 transform independently: they are rescaled but not mixed by a Lorentz boost. Their intensities acquire multiplicative factors $e^{\pm\psi}$, which are the relativistic Doppler factors for red- and blue-shifting of matter waves.

This result is significant: it shows that in the Weyl representation the relativistic transformation of spinors — normally introduced axiomatically in quantum field theory via the abstract operator $S(\Lambda)$ — arises here as a direct consequence of the biquaternion formalism. The Lorentz action is both diagonal and Doppler-like, linking the algebraic structure to the physical wave nature of spinor fields.

3.6 Lorentz transformations of the spinors in the Dirac representation environments

The same line of reasoning will give us the Lorentz transformation rules for the spinors in the space-time Dirac representation, respectively

$$\Psi_d^L = \Lambda_D\Psi_d = S\Lambda_W S^{-1}\Psi_d \quad (101)$$

and

$$(\Psi_d^L)^\dagger = (\Psi_d^\dagger)\Lambda_D = (\Psi_d^\dagger)S\Lambda_W S^{-1}. \quad (102)$$

For the intensities we then get

$$(\Psi_d^\dagger\Psi_d)^L = (\Psi_d^L)^\dagger\Psi_d^L = (\Psi_d^\dagger)\Lambda_D\Lambda_D\Psi_d = \quad (103)$$

$$(\Psi_d^\dagger)S\Lambda S^{-1}S\Lambda S^{-1}\Psi_d = (\Psi_d^\dagger)S\Lambda^2 S^{-1}\Psi_d. \quad (104)$$

In the Dirac representation, we have to calculate $S\Lambda^2 S^{-1}$ in order to be able to evaluate the result. In detail, with rapidity ψ , the operator $S\Lambda^2 S^{-1}$ is given as

$$S\Lambda^2 S^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \cosh(\psi)\hat{\mathbf{1}} & \sinh(\psi)\sigma_I \\ \sinh(\psi)\sigma_I & \cosh(\psi)\hat{\mathbf{1}} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbb{1} \cosh(\psi) + \alpha_I \sinh(\psi) = \mathbb{1} e^{(\alpha_I\psi)}, \quad (105)$$

with $\mathbb{1}e^{(\alpha_I\psi)}$ as the generator of the Lorentz boost delivered Doppler shift of the probability/field density, as

$$(\Psi^\dagger\Psi)^L = \Psi^\dagger e^{(\alpha_I\psi)}\Psi = \Psi^\dagger\Psi \cosh(\psi) + \Psi^\dagger\alpha_I\Psi \sinh(\psi). \quad (106)$$

The operator $\Lambda_D^2 = S\Lambda_W^2S^{-1}$ coincides with the original Dirac-spinor boost operator identified by Darwin (1928), confirming that the construction reproduces the standard result [22]. The intensity $\Psi^\dagger\Psi$ is not an invariant, but transforms covariantly with a Doppler factor, exactly as expected for a wave intensity.

Zooming in further and using $\cosh(\psi) = \gamma$ and $\sinh(\psi) = \gamma\beta$, we get for the Dirac representation

$$\begin{aligned} (\Psi^\dagger\Psi)^L &= [\Psi_1^* \Psi_2^* \Psi_3^* \Psi_4^*] \begin{bmatrix} \gamma & 0 & \gamma\beta & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma & 0 & -\gamma\beta \\ \gamma\beta & 0 & \gamma & 0 \\ 0 & -\gamma\beta & 0 & \gamma \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_1 \\ \Psi_2 \\ \Psi_3 \\ \Psi_4 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \gamma\Psi_1^*\Psi_1 + \gamma\beta\Psi_1^*\Psi_3 + \gamma\Psi_2^*\Psi_2 - \gamma\beta\Psi_2^*\Psi_4 \\ &\quad + \gamma\Psi_3^*\Psi_3 + \gamma\beta\Psi_3^*\Psi_1 + \gamma\Psi_4^*\Psi_4 - \gamma\beta\Psi_4^*\Psi_2. \end{aligned} \quad (107)$$

We see that in the Dirac representation, boosting the probability density mixes the spinors and thus the particles and the anti-particles, the electrons and the positrons. This mixing is what gives the Dirac representation its capacity to describe both particle and antiparticle solutions.

The structure of these transformations look familiar. If we define $\gamma' = \cosh(\frac{\psi}{2})$ and $\gamma'\beta' = \sinh(\frac{\psi}{2})$, we get the Lorentz transformation of Ψ as

$$\Psi^L = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma'\hat{\mathbf{1}} & \gamma'\beta'\sigma_I \\ \gamma'\beta'\sigma_I & \gamma'\hat{\mathbf{1}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Psi^1 \\ \Psi^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma'\hat{\mathbf{1}}\Psi^1 + \gamma'\beta'\sigma_I\Psi^2 \\ \gamma'\hat{\mathbf{1}}\Psi^2 + \gamma'\beta'\sigma_I\Psi^1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (108)$$

In the hyperbolic formulation, the details of the Lorentz transformation of Ψ gives

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi^L &= \begin{bmatrix} (\Psi^1)^L \\ (\Psi^2)^L \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cosh(\frac{\psi}{2})\hat{\mathbf{1}} & \sinh(\frac{\psi}{2})\sigma_I \\ \sinh(\frac{\psi}{2})\sigma_I & \cosh(\frac{\psi}{2})\hat{\mathbf{1}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Psi^1 \\ \Psi^2 \end{bmatrix} = \\ &\quad \begin{bmatrix} \cosh(\frac{\psi}{2})\hat{\mathbf{1}}\Psi^1 + \sinh(\frac{\psi}{2})\sigma_I\Psi^2 \\ \cosh(\frac{\psi}{2})\hat{\mathbf{1}}\Psi^2 + \sinh(\frac{\psi}{2})\sigma_I\Psi^1 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (109)$$

What we see here is that the Lorentz transformation of the Dirac spinor necessarily mixes the two twin Pauli spinors Ψ^1 and Ψ^2 . As a consequence, one cannot Lorentz transform a single Pauli spinor in the Dirac representation: a Lorentz transformation of the Pauli equation without its full Dirac twin is impossible. This shows that the Pauli equation on its own cannot possibly be relativistic – not

because of the Pauli matrices themselves, as is often suggested in the literature [23], but because a two-component spinor does not furnish a complete Lorentz representation.

While this fact is well known in relativistic quantum mechanics, the present construction provides a direct algebraic proof of it: by explicitly exhibiting how boosts act on the biquaternion/ β -matrix formalism, we see the unavoidable mixing of the two Pauli spinors. This constructive demonstration complements the usual argument (based on representation theory) and highlights the structural role of spinor doubling in the emergence of relativity at the Dirac level.

3.7 Connecting the β -matrices to the standard γ -, α - and spin-matrices

To make contact with the conventional Dirac formalism, we connect the β_μ of the minquat framework to the usual Clifford sets. Because our ordering of the Pauli matrices is reversed ($\sigma_I = \sigma_z$, $\sigma_J = \sigma_y$, $\sigma_K = \sigma_x$), the spatial γ -matrices inherit this relabeling:

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma} = (\gamma_I, \gamma_J, \gamma_K) = (\gamma_z, \gamma_y, \gamma_x).$$

In the Dirac representation, the $\gamma_\mu = (\gamma_0, \boldsymbol{\gamma})$ take their standard block form

$$\gamma_\mu = \left(\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{1}} & 0 \\ 0 & -\hat{\mathbf{1}} \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \boldsymbol{\sigma} \\ -\boldsymbol{\sigma} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right),$$

while in the Weyl representation one has

$$\gamma_\mu = \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \hat{\mathbf{1}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{1}} & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \boldsymbol{\sigma} \\ -\boldsymbol{\sigma} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right).$$

In the norm–spin basis $(\hat{\mathbf{1}}, \boldsymbol{\sigma})$ the Dirac α -matrices and the doubled Pauli spin set Σ_μ can be written as

$$\alpha_\mu = \left(\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{1}} & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{\mathbf{1}} \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \boldsymbol{\sigma} \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right), \quad \Sigma_\mu = \left(\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{1}} & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{\mathbf{1}} \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma} & 0 \\ 0 & \boldsymbol{\sigma} \end{bmatrix} \right).$$

Finally, the Clifford product is recovered directly:

$$-\beta_\mu \beta^\nu = \gamma_\mu \gamma^\nu = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{1} & -\boldsymbol{\alpha} \\ \boldsymbol{\alpha} & -\mathbb{1} \end{bmatrix} \rightsquigarrow \{\beta_\mu, \beta_\nu\} = 2\eta_{\mu\nu} \mathbb{1}.$$

Thus the β -matrices of the minquat construction reproduce the standard γ -algebra and its associated α and Σ structures. This confirms that the present framework dovetails with the familiar Dirac formalism while retaining its origin in the minquat–pauliquat duality.

4 Conclusion

In the Pauli-level part of this paper I introduced a biquaternion space-time metric that simultaneously respects the requirements of Minkowski space-time and incorporates the Pauli spin environment. Unlike the inert Minkowski metric η_μ , the space-time basis K_μ and its spin-norm dual σ_μ can be internally Doppler-twisted, so that dynamic vectors appear as $P_\mu K^\mu$. While the precise dimensional interpretation of the spin-norm dual remains open, the construction provides a consistent extension of Minkowski geometry.

On this foundation it was possible to reconstruct the Weyl–Dirac gamma-matrix environment directly from Pauli-level building blocks. By adding the PT dual to both K_μ and σ_μ I obtained the full Dirac representation and derived the Lorentz transformation operators constructively, rather than postulating them. This shows that Lorentz covariance of the Dirac equation emerges from the algebraic structure itself.

This framework also clarifies the often confusing status of the Dirac matrices. The Feynman-slash objects are best understood as the Weyl–Dirac analogues of Pauli-level dynamic vectors $P_\mu K^\mu$: in Lorentz transformations one either transforms the metric part K^μ or the dynamical part P_μ , but not both simultaneously. The gamma matrices thus encode the space-time metric in an indirect way and should not be interpreted as ordinary dynamic four-vectors.

The constructive approach developed here may be useful as background for teaching relativistic quantum mechanics. It highlights that the standard formalism of RQM, shaped by the Copenhagen interpretation, orders spectroscopic data without fully resolving its connection to physical reality. Making this connection clearer—by showing how Lorentz covariance can be derived from explicit space-time constructions—may help reduce the conceptual gap that still troubles students encountering RQM for the first time.

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